

Original article

In Right Colon Gunshot Injuries, Resection and Anastomosis Versus Primary Repair

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Ascending Colon
Simple Repair
Hemicolectomy
Anastomotic Leak

In case of ascending colon injuries, the predominant procedures are right hemicolectomy, ileocecal resection, and simple repair. The study has prospectively compared patients who have had right colon resection, with those who have had a simple repair due to gunshot injuries, to analyses the differences between both procedures in terms of post-operative outcomes. A cohort study was used to compare patients who had right colon resection, and patients who had a simple repair, to analyses the influence of the operative procedure on the short-term post-operative outcomes in all patients who had undergone urgent laparotomies following gunshot injuries to the right colon. This occurred during the time period from February 17, 2011 to December 31, 2018, in our department. Out of 65 patients, 63 (97%) were male and 2 (3%) were female, with a mean age of 29.3 years old. 43 (66.2%) patients had right colon resection and anastomosis, while 22 (33.8%) patients were treated by simple repair. Upon admission, 38 (58.5%) patients were in shock, 48 (73.8%) cases had faecal contamination, and 46 (70.8%) suffered from a multi-organ injury. According to the colon injury scale, in grade I there were 3 (4.6%) cases; while grade II, III, IV, V had 9 (13.8%), 35 (53.8%), 10 (15.4%) and 8 (12.3%) cases, respectively. The duration from the injury to the operation was less than 200 minutes in all cases. We have concluded that, in ascending colon injuries, there was no advantage of the simple repair over the hemicolectomy; therefore, it was not feasible to consider it as an acceptable safe alternative procedure.

Citation info. Mansor S, Alfitory M, Algialany A, Buzaja A, Eltarhoni A. In Right Colon Gunshot Injuries, Resection and Anastomosis Versus Primary Repair. *J Lib Sur Soc.* 2021;1(1):28-32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5792117>

INTRODUCTION

Following independence at the end of the Second World War, Libya never experienced war for many decades and gunshot injuries were uncommon. The peaceful state in this time period resulted in generations of surgeons who lacked sufficient experience to deal with the casualties of war and gunshot injuries. Therefore, the hard challenges faced by surgeons lies in the changes that have occurred in the past ten years, where guns have become prevalent in unauthorised and untrained hands, which has resulted in dramatic increases in incidences of gun-related violence [1]. In current time, gunshot injuries are common surgical cases and have become a major problem globally [1,2].

Colon wounds are common in penetrating abdominal gunshot injuries that have a high surgical and clinical significance due to the high risk of intra-abdominal septic complications [1]. At the beginning of the twentieth century, colon wounds were almost fatal with mortality

rates reaching 90%; patients either died from their primary injuries or from septic complications [3]. In World War I, with the beginning of gaining some experience in treating colon injuries, mortality rates fell to 70%; subsequently, by World War II, colostomy creation was adopted as the standard management of penetrating colon injuries that led to mortality rates that fell to 35% [4], until Stone and Fabian confirmed the safety of primary repair for colon wounds in selected cases [5]. Despite the evolution in operative techniques and improvements in antimicrobial therapy during wartime, as well as in civil experiences that have brought a remarkable decline in both colon-related morbidity and mortality, the management of colonic injuries has always been a dilemma for surgeons, and there remains some debate regarding its management, although it has still undergone progressive evolution with the experience gained.

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The simple repairs, segmental colectomy with anastomosis, and colon diversion are considered the principles of treatment for colon injuries in general, but in the case of ascending colon injuries specifically, the most commonly performed procedures are right hemicolectomy, ileocecal resection with anastomosis, or a simple repair (Figure 1). In the current study, the post-operative outcomes have prospectively been compared between patients who have had right colon resection and anastomosis, with those who have had a simple repair in patients who suffered gunshot injuries at the right colon, with the aim to assess and analyses the differences between both procedures in terms of feasibility and rates of postoperative outcomes to determine whether simple repairs could be accepted as a beneficial alternative procedure to the right colectomy with anastomosis.

Fig 1. Types of operative procedure in right colon injury

METHODS

A cohort study was conducted to compare patients who had right colon resection with anastomosis, who were considered the first group, and patients who had a simple repair, who were considered the second group. Subsequently, this was undertaken in order to analyse the influence of the type of operative procedure on the short-term post-operative outcomes in all patients who had undergone urgent laparotomies following gunshot injuries at the right colon. This was set in the time period from February 17, 2011 to December 31, 2018, in our department; Table 1 demonstrates the baseline characteristics of the patients in both groups included in the study.

All patients were resuscitated following the protocols of the Advanced Trauma Life Support of the American College of Surgeons. Additionally, patients' data was taken, such as: age, gender, shock upon admission, blood transfusion, colon injury scores, faecal contamination, associated injured organs, past medical history, surgical procedures, the delay time before the operation, duration of the operation, post-operative complications, the indication of re-operation and procedures in re-operation, which were considered as risk factors. The primary endpoint was an appearance of any short-term post-operative complications.

All patients undergoing primary repair of the right colon, ileocecal resection, right hemicolectomy, and extended right hemicolectomy as an emergency operation approach during the study period were included. Meanwhile, all

patients who had a right colon procedure, repairs or resection as part of a bigger procedure, such as subtotal colectomy were excluded, or if the distal colonic transaction point was beyond the splenic flexure, as well as patients who had multiple site colon injuries and destructive colon injuries with loss of its own segmental blood supply were also excluded.

During the statistical analysis, all continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). The categorical data were expressed as frequency and percentage. Comparisons between groups were made using the X² test or Fisher exact test for categorical variables as appropriate. Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS v21 statistical software and p values of less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. In addition, during the process of the study, informed consent was required, as the hospital is a teaching university hospital; thus, written informed consents were routinely signed and obtained from all admitted patients or legally authorized representatives during the hospital stay and prior to their inclusion in the study, in order to use patients' data and to be published in academic activities and researches. Further, ethical approval was approved by the Medical Affairs Office of the Al-Jalaa teaching hospital, Benghazi University.

RESULTS

In the current study, out of 65 patients, 63 (97%) were male and 2 (3%) were female, with a mean age of 29.3 years old. 43 (66.2%) patients were treated by right colon resection and anastomosis, which was considered the first group in the study, while the second group comprised 22 (33.8%) patients, who had the simple repair of the right colonic wall (Table 1). Upon admission to the hospital, 38 (58.5%) patients were in shock; 48 (73.8%) cases had faecal contamination; and 46 (70.8%) suffered from a multi-organ injury.

Table 1. The baseline characteristics of the patients in both groups included in the study

Basic Characteristic	Right colon resection	Right colon simple repair	P value
Mean age (Years)	28	31.7	0.261
Body mass index (Mean)	23.7	21.6	0.732
Male: Female ratio (No)	42:1	21:1	0.624
History of Cigarette Smoking (No, %)	36 (83.7%)	20 (90.9%)	0.427
History of Hypertension (No, %)	1 (2.3%)	2 (9.0%)	0.218
History of Diabetes Miletus (No, %)	2 (4.6%)	1 (9.0%)	0.496
Multi injured organs (No, %)	28 (65.1%)	18 (81.8%)	0.161
Shoch on admission (No, %)	24 (55.8%)	14 (63.6%)	0.545
Total cases (No)	43	22	

According to the colon injury scale, in grade I there were 3 (4.6%) cases, grade II had 9 (13.8%), grade III totaled 35 (53.8%), grade IV had 10 (15.4%), and grade V with 8 (12.3%) cases. The delay time from the injury to the operation was less than 200 minutes in all cases. The rate of post-operative complications in the first group was 37.2%, while in the second group it was 37.5%. Table 2 shows the details of post-operative complications in both groups.

Table 2. Rate and type of postoperative complications in both groups

Postoperative complication	Right colon resection	Right colon simple repair
Wound infection	8	3
incisional hernia	4	2
intra-abdominal abscess	3	1
burst abdomen	2	2
Postoperative ileus	2	2
Massil tract infection	2	0
Colo-cutaneous fistula	2	0
Anastomosis leak	1	0
Septic shock	1	0
Pneumonia	1	0
Biliary leak	0	1
Atelectasis	1	0
Acute renal failure	1	0
Hypoalbuminemia	0	1
Seroma	0	1
DVT	1	0

Operative re-exploration was conducted on ten patients in total in both groups. In the first group, seven patients (16.2%) were re-operated, with the indication of re-exploration was due to the formation of an intra-abdominal abscess in four patients, while the burst abdomen was the reason in other two patients. Additionally, one patient was due to an anastomotic leak, and in the last patient, the indication of a second analysis was the removal of abdominal backing as a part of damage control surgery. Meanwhile, in the second group, the re-exploration occurred in three cases (13.6%), with two of them because of the burst abdomen and the last patient due to intra-abdominal abscess formation. In the current study, there was no significant statistical differences between the type of surgical procedures and the rate of post-operative complications, as well as reoperation rates, respectively ($P=0.423$ & 0.78).

DISCUSSION

The evolution in the management of colon trauma has occurred from wartime experiences; while military practices had a clear impact on the improvement in civilian care. During the past four decades, trauma surgeons have refined techniques in the management of colon injuries, as well as developments in evidence-based approaches to these injuries, which eventually led to improvements in patient morbidity and mortality [4]. Through this large volume of experiences, it became clear that the colon is commonly injured from penetrating

trauma in the civilian, as well as in military settings, where the vast majority of injuries are because of gunshot wounds. In penetrating colon injuries, the transverse colon is the most commonly injured segment, while the right colon is involved in a significant rate of cases [6]. Despite all of that and with an abundance of quality evidence regarding the management of colon injury obtained, controversy still exists regarding the management of these injuries.

In general, the principle of colon injury management ranges from simple repair, colon resection with anastomosis, and colon diversion according to many factors as the Hemodynamic state of the patient, type and grade of injury, degree of faecal contamination, and time between the initial injury and operation, with a significant rate of morbidity and mortality. Recently many studies have been unable to find any advantage of the diversion over the primary repair. Therefore, they prefer primary repair, and have accepted it as an alternative method of treatment to colon injury over the colostomy creation to reduce the risk of psychological trauma, the complication of colostomy, unnecessary repeated hospitalisation, a decrease in economic costs, and complications of the stoma revision operation [7]. It was also concluded that shock state upon admission and blood transfusion are considered predictive risk factors for post-operative complications in patients with gunshot penetrating injuries to the colon [8].

The right colon has its own anatomic and physiologic features, as its contents are liquid, which has a large lumen with a thin wall, and derives its blood supply from the superior mesenteric artery. Moreover, its retroperitoneal fixed position with its closed anatomical relationship to the ileum, which is a relatively free intraperitoneal organ with broad mesentery that provides a wide range of mobility without tension, lead to the reduction in the risk of anastomotic leaks, which may make right colon suture lines more likely to heal than those of the left colon. In the case of right colon injury, the primary repair, and resection with anastomosis are the predominant procedures for treatment [9]; comparatively, some literature has mentioned that the colostomy procedure is one of the treatment methods [10,11].

During the surgical exploration of a patient who has a right colon penetrating injury, the grade of injury needs to be assessed by the adequate mobilization of the injured segment and the entire side of the colon, in order to examine its posterior wall, as well as the adjacent organs. Further, small injuries can be diagnosed by the leak of bowel contents following compression of the colonic segment. If primary repairs of penetrating colon injury are to be performed, adequate debridement of the wound should initially occur, particularly in gunshot wounds. It is important to ensure well-perfused edges before any repair is performed, which are subsequently typically closed in two layers using absorbable sutures. While performing segment resection with anastomosis, healthy viable edges should be exposed and the creation of a tension-free anastomosis, which always occurs in the right-side colon because it is anastomosis with freely

mobile rich blood supply ileum.

The seriousness of the post-operative complications in case of colon injuries, which is known as colon related complications, lies in the fact that they are septic in nature, with many international research studies in recent years in the era of penetrating colon injuries concluding colon related abdominal complication rates between 15–50 % [12, 13]. Meanwhile, the major adverse outcomes post-operation for colon injuries are wound infections, fascial dehiscence, intra-abdominal abscess, anastomotic leaks, and missile tract infections (Table 2), which may all lead to prolonged hospitalisation and increased management costs [7,8].

Many studies have reported clear evidence, and all agree that hypovolemic shock is the most critical predictive risk factor for complications [7,8,14,15]. A decrease in colon blood supply, causing a state of insufficient colonic mucosal perfusion with cellular ischemia and hypoxia, with the added effect of bacterial colonisation at the site of injury, can lead to the failure of healing after colon repair [16]. What is more, any repair or anastomosis performed in an ischemic bowel and contaminated abdomen has a risk of leakage; while the anastomotic leak rate in an ischemic colon is approximately 35% higher than rates seen in elective surgery [17,18]. Despite adequate perfusion in the right hemicolectomy procedure, due to the ileocolic artery blood supply, some studies have reported the leak rate of 4% in ileocolonic anastomosis [19].

Surgical management of gunshot injuries with colon wounds relates to contaminated procedures with an inherent risk of gross contamination of the peritoneal cavity and incision [20]. In a prospective study of patients who have undergone colon resection, the rates of wound infection and intra-abdominal abscesses were 8%, and 3.8%, respectively [21]. While some other studies illustrated that the mortality for patients with an intra-abdominal abscess after colorectal operations was significantly higher than in patients without an intra-abdominal abscess (19 versus 4 %) [22]. Post-operative ileus refers to the state of intolerance of oral intake due to disrupting the normal coordinated motor activity of the gastrointestinal tract [23]. Furthermore, there is general consensus that some degree of post-operative ileus is a normal physiologic response to abdominal surgery that resolves without serious sequelae [24]. Some theories demonstrate that post-operative ileus following abdominal surgery appears to result from an inflammatory response to intestinal manipulation and trauma. Previous international studies have shown that the degree of intestinal manipulation is directly related to both the degree of leukocyte infiltration into the intestinal muscularis and the amount of intestinal dysmotility [25]. Peters et al. have shown in their prospective trial that inflammatory parameters in blood samples are increased in post-operative ileus patients who undergo colorectal surgery.

CONCLUSION

In the operative management for ascending colon gunshot injuries, it was not possible to determine any advantage

of the simple colonic wall repair over the segmental colonic resection with anastomosis; therefore, it has not been possible to consider it as an acceptable safe alternative method of treatment in terms of post-operative complications.

Conflict of interests

There are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Funding

This work is not funded.

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